

Animal Model with Fixed Effects of block & population

FINAL MODEL with Fixed effects – USED IN MS

```
# Load model output
load(file = "IP2_animModel_1M_thin5K_x6_fixedEffects.RData")

### Summarize each run of model
summary(model_6chains[[1]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21101.36
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal      0.46  0.1844  0.8714      180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1349  0.0868  0.2033      180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.66609 -0.85147 -0.52272  129.2 <0.006 **
## block2      0.09426 -0.03645  0.22293  180.0  0.189
## popF:M      0.57707  0.43829  0.74872  288.2 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.82212  0.61565  1.03588  704.5 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.45517  1.11345  1.68292  124.5 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[2]])
```

```

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21104.55
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal      0.438  0.09162   0.755     180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam         0.1346  0.07875   0.1965     180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units         1         1         1         0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.66419 -0.79332 -0.52474     180 <0.006 **
## block2       0.09172 -0.02461  0.19805     180  0.111
## popF:M       0.58534  0.40988  0.72206     180 <0.006 **
## popM:F       0.81502  0.62796  1.03385     180 <0.006 **
## popM:M       1.45310  1.23585  1.66922     180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[3]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21097.75
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal      0.4617  0.1774   0.7646     180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp

```

```

## dam      0.133  0.07758  0.2034  275.7
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.66438 -0.82494 -0.52454 180 <0.006 **
## block2      0.08821 -0.06191  0.23241 180  0.233
## popF:M      0.57124  0.43690  0.74230 180 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.82744  0.59110  1.03146 180 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.46474  1.25835  1.72814 180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[4]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21103
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal      0.4415  0.2034  0.6931 180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1354  0.09411  0.1888 180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.673531 -0.815779 -0.507110 180.0 <0.006 **
## block2      0.101248 -0.006075  0.249750 180.0  0.122
## popF:M      0.582768  0.405026  0.741724 230.7 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.814464  0.599513  0.995302 180.0 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.453743  1.248653  1.703722 180.0 <0.006 **

```

```
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[5]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21103.13
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4504  0.1497  0.7692    180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1371  0.08498  0.2035    222.4
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.67152 -0.79598 -0.50308    180.0 <0.006 **
## block2      0.09762 -0.02803  0.23169    180.0  0.156
## popF:M      0.57671  0.43410  0.79381    192.3 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.81249  0.60401  1.03408    180.0 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.46511  1.26252  1.75711    134.3 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[6]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21105.27
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4178  0.1941  0.7087    224.1
```

```

##
##           ~dam
##
##      post.mean 1-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1372  0.08317  0.1781   177.7
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean 1-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units          1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean 1-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.65901 -0.81199 -0.54749   180.0 <0.006 **
## block2      0.09370 -0.01896  0.23414   180.0  0.167
## popF:M      0.57040  0.39772  0.72517   180.0 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.80395  0.62807  0.96739   180.0 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.43754  1.24670  1.68444   141.5 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

### Summarize 6 chains
animCh1 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
animCh2 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)
animCh3 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)
animCh4 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)
animCh5 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)
animCh6 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

ES_VCV_Ch1 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch2 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch3 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch4 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch5 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch6 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

library(dplyr)
resultsVCV <- bind_rows(animCh1, animCh2, animCh3, animCh4, animCh5, animCh6)
ES_VCV <- bind_rows(ES_VCV_Ch1, ES_VCV_Ch2, ES_VCV_Ch3, ES_VCV_Ch4,
ES_VCV_Ch5, ES_VCV_Ch6)

SolCh1 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)
SolCh2 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[2]]$Sol)
SolCh3 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[3]]$Sol)
SolCh4 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[4]]$Sol)
SolCh5 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[5]]$Sol)
SolCh6 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[6]]$Sol)

ES_Sol_Ch1 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)

```

```

ES_Sol_Ch2 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[2]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch3 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[3]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch4 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[4]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch5 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[5]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch6 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[6]]$Sol)

resultsSol <- bind_rows(SolCh1, SolCh2, SolCh3, SolCh4, SolCh5, SolCh6)
ES_Sol <- bind_rows(ES_Sol_Ch1, ES_Sol_Ch2, ES_Sol_Ch3, ES_Sol_Ch4,
ES_Sol_Ch5, ES_Sol_Ch6)

ES_Sol

## # A tibble: 6 × 5
##   `(Intercept)` block2 `popF:M` `popM:F` `popM:M`
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 129. 180 288. 705. 125.
## 2 180 180 180 180 180
## 3 180 180 180 180. 180
## 4 180 180 231. 180. 180
## 5 180 180 192. 180 134.
## 6 180. 180 180 180 141.

ES_VCV

## # A tibble: 6 × 3
##   animal dam units
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 180 180 0
## 2 180 180 0
## 3 180 276. 0
## 4 180 180 0
## 5 180 222. 0
## 6 224. 178. 0

heidel.diag(as.mcmc(resultsVCV))

##
##   Stationarity start p-value
##   test iteration
## animal passed 109 0.0784
## dam passed 1 0.3338
## units failed NA NA
##
##   Halfwidth Mean Halfwidth
##   test
## animal passed 0.442 0.00997
## dam passed 0.135 0.00167
## units <NA> NA NA

### BELOW USED TO CHECK MIXING OF CHAINS IN PARALLEL
animalChains <- cbind(animCh1, animCh2, animCh3, animCh4, animCh5, animCh6)

```

```
names(anim1Chains) <- c("anim1", "dam1", "unit1", "anim2", "dam2", "unit2",
"anim3",
  "dam3", "unit3", "anim4", "dam4", "unit4", "anim5", "dam5", "unit5",
"anim6",
  "dam6", "unit6")
base <- ggplot(anim1Chains, aes(x = as.numeric(row.names(anim1Chains)), y =
anim1,
  group = 3)) + geom_path()

base + geom_path(aes(x = as.numeric(row.names(anim1Chains)), y = anim2,
group = 1),
  colour = "blue") + geom_path(aes(x = as.numeric(row.names(anim1Chains)),
y = anim3,
  group = 1), colour = "green") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(anim1Chains)),
  y = anim4, group = 1), colour = "red") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(anim1Chains)),
  y = anim5, group = 1), colour = "orange") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(anim1Chains)),
  y = anim6, group = 1), colour = "maroon1")
```



```
### Check autocorrs
autocorr(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.46885462  NaN
```

```

## Lag 5000      0.10049896 -0.04941464   NaN
## Lag 25000    -0.06992310  0.03388448   NaN
## Lag 50000    -0.08338115 -0.03695162   NaN
## Lag 250000   0.03515583  0.04040418   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##           animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.46885462  1.000000000   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.08592166 -0.086021626   NaN
## Lag 25000  0.05197716 -0.002593264   NaN
## Lag 50000  0.06584581  0.007062697   NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.02113522  0.059366410   NaN
##
## , , units
##
##           animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##           animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.000000000 -0.49045021   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.005897082 -0.10701641   NaN
## Lag 25000  0.072660472  0.02522482   NaN
## Lag 50000  0.012523218 -0.08407887   NaN
## Lag 250000 0.055846429 -0.07059524   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##           animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.49045021  1.000000000   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.04087456 -0.005841392   NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.10862682  0.018020132   NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.08009974  0.142449988   NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.04626336  0.019746968   NaN
##
## , , units
##
##           animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN   NaN

```

```
## Lag 50000      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000    NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##           animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.58453560   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.02204744  0.15592906   NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.05544746  0.05576682   NaN
## Lag 50000  0.09520423 -0.09438940   NaN
## Lag 250000 0.09233206 -0.06586083   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##           animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.584535598  1.00000000   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.016908536 -0.03715738   NaN
## Lag 25000  0.018986149 -0.04238642   NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.086048950  0.03647524   NaN
## Lag 250000 0.002904104 -0.06554264   NaN
##
## , , units
##
##           animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##           animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.35866316   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.0352607  0.04165223   NaN
## Lag 25000  0.1746895  -0.05791989   NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.0706328 -0.02877601   NaN
## Lag 250000 0.1398447 -0.09576737   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##           animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -3.586632e-01  1.000000000   NaN
## Lag 5000    2.084136e-01 -0.004838543   NaN
## Lag 25000  -6.400020e-02  0.037223122   NaN
## Lag 50000  7.859681e-05  0.058840331   NaN
## Lag 250000 -9.635752e-02  0.013362128   NaN
```

```

##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 5000    NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 25000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 50000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000  NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.51370257   NaN
## Lag 5000    0.01059219  0.10163728   NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.07423919  0.05626367   NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.02874944 -0.08596327   NaN
## Lag 250000 0.04810885 -0.06404372   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0     -0.51370257  1.00000000   NaN
## Lag 5000   0.03241924 -0.108210882  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.01315757 -0.050397749  NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.02789892 -0.009556501  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.10991841  0.060249746  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 5000    NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 25000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 50000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000  NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.37436244   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.11192732  0.14048505   NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.07492954 -0.02044821   NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.01131303 -0.00616718   NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.07764107  0.05772564   NaN
##
## , , dam

```

```
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.374362439  1.000000000  NaN
## Lag 5000   0.169352447 -0.055738554  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.004586389  0.149590639  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.033702641 -0.080834400  NaN
## Lag 250000 0.093206955 -0.007459409  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

require(QGglm)
n <- length(resultsSol$`(Intercept)`)
mu <- mean(resultsSol$`(Intercept)`)
va <- mean(resultsVVCV$animal)
vd <- mean(resultsVVCV$dam)
vp <- mean(rowSums(resultsVVCV))

QGparams(mu = mu, var.a = va, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.probit")

## [1] "Using the closed forms for a Binomial1 - probit model."

##   mean.obs  var.obs  var.a.obs  h2.obs
## 1 0.3391102 0.2241145 0.02310197 0.1030811

QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = vd, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.probit")

## [1] "Using a semi-closed form for a binom1.probit model."

## Warning in QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = vd, var.p = vp, model =
## "binom1.probit"): Some component (var.comp.obs) are not totally
## from a closed form solution: an integral is computed

##   mean.obs  var.obs  var.comp.obs  icc.obs
## 1 0.3391102 0.2241145 0.007064557 0.03152209

library(purrr)
X1 <- model_6chains[[1]][["X"]]
t <- model_6chains[[1]][["Sol"]]

## multiply each row of fixed effects solutions by design matrix predict is a
## list the length of the sample size & each element of the list has the same
## length as the length of the fixed effect matrix
```

```

predict1 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[1]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[1]][["Sol"]][.,
  ]))

predict2 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[2]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[2]][["Sol"]][.,
  ]))

predict3 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[3]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[3]][["Sol"]][.,
  ]))

predict4 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[4]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[4]][["Sol"]][.,
  ]))

predict5 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[5]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[5]][["Sol"]][.,
  ]))

predict6 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[6]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[6]][["Sol"]][.,
  ]))

predict <- c(predict1, predict2, predict3, predict4, predict5, predict6)

paramsPFE <- pmap_dfr(list(predict = predict, var.a = resultsVCV$animal,
var.p = rowSums(resultsVCV) -
  1), QGparams, model = "binom1.probit", verbose = FALSE)

mean(paramsPFE[["h2.obs"]])
## [1] 0.1458881

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(paramsPFE[["h2.obs"]]))
##           lower      upper
## var1 0.07385115 0.2179872
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

##### See tutorial by de Villemereuil 2021 'Estimation of a biological
trait...'
##### (in Zotero collection 'Animal Model')

## Heritability on Liability scale
herit_liab <- resultsVCV$animal/rowSums(resultsVCV)
mean(herit_liab)

```

```

## [1] 0.2749719

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(herit_liab))

##           lower      upper
## var1 0.1467379 0.4240107
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

compute_varpred <- function(beta, design_matrix) {
  ## deVille 2021 p. 26
  var(as.vector(design_matrix %*% beta))
}

## Next line from de Villemereuil 2021 tutorial, p. 27
vf <- apply(resultsSol, 1, compute_varpred, design_matrix = X1) ## X1 is
design matrix from model - see line 106 above
herit_FE <- resultsVCV$animal/(rowSums(resultsVCV) + vf)
mean(herit_FE)

## [1] 0.2315265          Corrected for fixed effects

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(herit_FE))

##           lower      upper
## var1 0.1168529 0.3453576
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

#### Below is from deVillemereuil2021 (zotero) - tutorial 2, Section 4.2, p.
37

### Heritability on Observed scale pmap_dfr is a purrr function that works
### similarly to mapply
library(purrr)
paramsB <- pmap_dfr(list(mu = resultsSol$(Intercept), var.a =
resultsVCV$animal,
  var.p = rowSums(resultsVCV) + vf), QGparams, model = "binom1.probit",
verbose = FALSE)
mean(paramsB[["h2.obs"]])

## [1] 0.09126637

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(paramsB[["h2.obs"]]))

##           lower      upper
## var1 0.04729784 0.1476778
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

plot(as.mcmc(resultsVCV$animal))

```



```
heidel.diag(as.mcmc(resultsVCV))  
  
##  
##      Stationarity start      p-value  
##      test      iteration  
## animal passed      109      0.0784  
## dam      passed      1      0.3338  
## units failed      NA      NA  
##  
##      Halfwidth Mean      Halfwidth  
##      test  
## animal passed      0.442 0.00997  
## dam      passed      0.135 0.00167  
## units <NA>      NA      NA  
  
library(coda)  
library(lattice)  
densityplot(as.mcmc(paramsB[["h2.obs"]]))
```

